

A green chemistry approach to the synthesis of isatoic anhydrides from anthranilic acid derivatives

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Abstract : An efficient one pot synthesis of isatoic anhydrides (2a-g) from anthranilic acid derivatives (1a-g) using triphosgene over basic alumina, under solvent free conditions with microwave heating is described.

Keywords : Green chemistry, synthesis - microwave technique, anthranilic acid derivatives.

Isatoic anhydrides have been extensively employed as inexpensive versatile agents in the synthesis of wide variety of biologically active heterocyclic compounds¹. Recently, triphosgene has been employed with good success as a substitute to phosgene in cyclocondensation reaction². A typical conventional run for the synthesis of isatoic anhydride required refluxing of anthranilic acid with a carbonic acid derivative to an extended period in an organic solvent. The process needed a tedious work up procedure of isolation and produced isatoic anhydride in a low yield.

The use of microwave irradiation for carrying out organic reactions has been well established and have recently been reviewed³. The use of dry media in synthesis under microwave irradiation especially the use of supported reagents on mineral oxides has been a promising alternative to environmentally unacceptable usage of solvents in thermal procedures. The application of the solvent free technology coupled with the recyclability of mineral support has led to the development of many reaction procedures which are environment friendly, falling in the domain of Green Chemistry⁴. One such approach to the synthesis of isatoic anhydride (2a-g) from anthranilic acid (1a-g) is described in this paper.

Results and discussion

MW irradiation of the mixture of anthranilic acids (1a-g) and triphosgene over the basic alumina support produced isatoic anhydrides (2a-g) in an excellent yield. In a typical run, a slurry of anthranilic acid 1a (1.0 mmol), triphosgene (9.66 mmol) and basic alumina (1.0 mmol) was prepared in dioxane (5.0 ml). The dried slurry was

powdered and the free flowing powder was placed in a 100 ml borosil beaker, in an alumina bath and irradiated at 720 W for 10 min. The temperature of the reaction mixture inside the alumina bath reached 110 °C. (However, the temperature of the reaction mixture when alumina bath was not used reached to only 45 °C). The completion of the reaction was checked by TLC. The organic product was extracted from the inorganic solid support with chloroform (3 × 5 ml). Evaporation of the chloroform layer gave 2a (75%).

The solid support (basic alumina) is recyclable and can be used several times without loss of activity, after washing with diethyl ether and finally drying in an oven at 100 °C. To optimize the results, the reactions were carried out in different molar ratio and with different amounts of solid support. It was observed that 1.0 mmol of anthranilic acid and 0.66 mmol of triphosgene gave best results. The amount of alumina was also crucial for the smooth reaction. It was found that for 1.0 mmol of anthranilic acid, 1.0 g of basic alumina was required. The power levels 720 W of MW for 10 min gave the best results. Suitability of different solid support was also examined by conducting the reaction with acidic, basic, neutral alumina and silica powder. The results are summarized in Table 1.

To our knowledge there has been no report on the synthesis of isatoic anhydrides from anthranilic acids using triphosgene under MW conditions. Therefore, to check the possible intervention of specific (non-thermal) MW effect, the results of the MW irradiation were compared with the conventional heating (Table 2). Thus, the reaction of 1a with triphosgene was carried out under a pre-

Table 1. Reaction of anthranilic acid (**1a**) with triphosgene using different solid supports under MW conditions

Microwave induced method (medium)	MW power (watts)	Time (min)	Temp. ^a (°C)	Yield ^b (%)
Basic alumina	720	10	110	75
Acidic alumina	720	16	95	60
Neutral alumina	720	18	90	55
Silica powder	720	14	90	58
Neat	720	16	65	Nil

^aTemperature was noted at the end of exposure during microwave experiment by immersing glass thermometer into the reaction mixture and gives an approximate temperature range.

^bYield of isolated products.

Table 2. Yield of isatoic anhydrides (**2a-g**) by the reaction of anthranilic acids (**1a-g**) with triphosgene under conventional and MW irradiation conditions

Entry product	Reaction temp. ^a (°C)		Time (min)		Yield ^b (%)		Found m.p./lit (m.p.)
	Convt. ^c	MW	Convt. ^c	MW	Convt. ^c	MW	
2a	Reflux	110	480	9	58.26	75	204/206 ⁶
2b	Reflux	103	480	10	50.23	73	248/249.15 ⁷
2c	Reflux	108	480	10	53	71	255 ⁹ /256.31 ⁸
2d	Reflux	107	480	11	55.78	69	285/287.15 ⁹
2e	Reflux	110	480	8	49.49	70	305/305.43 ¹⁰
2f	Reflux	109	480	9	42	65	235 ⁹ /236.59 ¹¹
2g	Reflux	110	480	11	45	68	308/308.91 ¹²

^aTemperature was noted at the end of exposure during microwave experiment by immersing glass thermometer into the reaction mixture and gives an approximate temperature range.

^bYield of isolated product.

^cConventional method (solvent dioxane).

heated oil-bath without the MW irradiation. It was found that there was no reaction and the reactants remained unchanged even after prolonged heating.

From this observation, two features of the reaction are clearly apparent. The effect of MW was not simply thermal and secondly the reaction under solvent free conditions required a solid support to be present for the transmission of energy (Table 1).

Authentic samples of **2a-g** were prepared by known methods². Their formation under MW conditions was confirmed by mixed melting point, co-tlc and superimposable IR spectra.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. TLC was done on silica gel 'G' coated glass plates using benzene : methanol (9.5 : 0.5) as eluent of the reactions. IR spectra on KBr were

1a 4-Cl	2a 7-Cl
b 3,5-Cl, Cl	b 6,8-Cl, Cl
c 4,5-OMe, OMe	c 6,7-OMe, OMe
d 6-NO ₂	d 5-NO ₂
e 3,5-I, I	e 6,8-I, I
f 5-Br	f 6-Br
g 3,5-Br, Br	g 6,8-Br, Br

Scheme 1

recorded on FTIR-8400S, CE(SHIMADZU). Microwave reactions were carried out on LG MC-808 WAR model, operating at 720 W, generating 2550 MHz frequency.

General procedure :

A slurry of **1a-g** (1 mmol), triphosgene (0.66 mmol, 0.195 g) was prepared in a minimum quantity of dioxane (5 ml) and was adsorbed on a basic alumina solid support. The slurry was dried in a rotatory evaporator and was powdered with the help of a pestle in a mortar.

The dry free flowing powder was taken in a Borosil beaker (100 ml) and was kept on an alumina bath⁵ and irradiated to an appropriate time (Table 1). The temperature of the reaction inside the alumina bath had reached 100° whereas in the neat reaction without using alumina bath could attain only 45°. The organic product from the inorganic solid support was separated by extracting it with chloroform (3 × 5 ml). Solvent was evaporated to give crystals of **2a-g**, which were found sufficiently pure on TLC. The resulting solid was washed with hot dioxane and dried.

2a (75%), m.p. 204° (lit. 206°)⁶; ν_{\max} 3180 (NH), 1761 (CO), 1720 (CONH), 780 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 8 (1H, s, NH), 7.22–8.05 (3H, m, ArH); **2b** (73%), m.p. 248° (lit. 249.15°)⁷; ν_{\max} 3181 (NH), 1760 (CO), 1721 (CONH), 782 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 8 (1H, s, NH), 7.80 (1H, s, ArH⁵), 7.60 (1H, s, ArH⁷); **2c** (71%), m.p. 255° (lit. 256.31°)⁸; ν_{\max} 3178 (NH), 1760 (CO), 1718 (CONH), 1375 and 1460 (O-CH₃); δ 8 (1H, s, NH), 7.51 (1H, s, ArH⁵), 7.25 (1H, s, ArH⁸), 3.73 (6H, s, OCH₃); **2d** (69%), m.p. 285° (lit. 287.15°)⁹; ν_{\max} 3181 (NH), 1762 (CO), 1722 (CONH), 1350 and 1550 cm^{-1} (C-NO₂); δ 8 (1H, s, NH), 8.14–8.24 (3H, m, ArH); **2e** (70%), m.p. 305° (lit. 305.43°)¹⁰; ν_{\max} 3180 (NH), 1760 (CO), 1719 (CONH), 500 cm^{-1} (C-I); δ 8 (1H, s, NH), 8.48 (1H, s, ArH⁵), 8.34 (1H, s, ArH⁷); **2f** (65%), m.p. 235° (lit. 236.59°)¹¹; ν_{\max} 3180 (NH), 1761 (CO), 1720 (CONH), 740 cm^{-1} (C-Br); δ 8 (1H, s, NH), 8.28 (1H, s, ArH⁵), 7.75 (2H, s, ArH^{7,8}); **2g** (68%), m.p. 308° (lit. 308.91°)¹²; ν_{\max} 3181 (NH), 1761 (CO), 1721 (CONH), 780 cm^{-1} (C-Br); δ 8 (1H, s, NH), 8.22 (1H, s, ArH⁵), 7.92 (1H, s, ArH⁷).

Same reaction was performed on neutral alumina, acidic alumina and silica powder and the results are given in Table 1.

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